

FLEXURAL MODULUS REDUCTION DUE TO MATRIX CRACKING DAMAGE IN A GFRP CROSS-PLY LAMINATE

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SUMMARY

Cross-ply (0/90₂/0/90₂/0) glass fibre/epoxy laminates, incorporating two transverse plies symmetrically arranged about the neutral axis, have been tested in flexure under both quasi-static and fatigue loading. In all cases, matrix cracks develop from the 0/90 interface on the tensile side of the coupon and grow both across the transverse ply thickness towards the neutral axis and across the coupon width. For fatigue loading at a “high” load level, additional damage in the form of delaminations, which develop from matrix cracks at the free edge, and fracture of 0⁰ fibre bundles on the tensile face at the coupon edge, were also observed. Measured reductions in the flexural modulus as a result of matrix cracking damage were in good agreement with a previously published model, except where additional damage (*i.e.* delaminations and surface fibre bundle fractures) occurred.

KEY TERMS: Cross-ply laminates, Flexural modulus, Crack density, Four-point bending, Fatigue

1. INTRODUCTION

The flexural properties of composite laminates have received less attention than their tensile characteristics, although there is a growing literature on testing composite laminates in flexure and associated results^{1,2,3,4}. With reference to cross-ply laminates in particular, there is much literature on tensile loading dealing with the development of matrix cracks and their effect on residual properties (e.g.^{5,6,7}), and much less work in flexure. Analytical models have been proposed recently by several authors^{8,9} describing the decrease of flexural modulus of a cross-ply laminate as a result of progressive cracking of one 90° ply under simple bending. The predictions of these two models for the flexural modulus as a function of crack density for a (0/90₂/0/90₂/0) laminate differ by less than 1%.

This work is part of an experimental study on the behaviour of a (0/90₂/0/90₂/0) glass fibre/epoxy laminate tested in four-point bending under quasi-static and fatigue loading. The development of matrix cracking during quasi-static and fatigue loading has been investigated, together with the relationship between changes in flexural modulus and increasing crack density.

2. MATERIALS AND TEST METHODS

A (0/90₂/0/90₂/0) laminate lay up was chosen for this study, each ply having a thickness of about 0.5 mm. Rectangular panels were manufactured by dry winding E-glass roving onto a square steel frame and impregnating with epoxy resin. Details of the laminate fabrication technique can be found elsewhere (e.g.¹⁰). Test coupons 20 mm wide were cut from the laminates and used in quasi-static and

fatigue loading flexural tests under four-point bending. All the tests were carried out using a computer controlled Instron 8000 servo-hydraulic testing machine. Fatigue tests were carried out at 3 Hz for two different load levels: 26.5 Nm (“low” load) and 34 Nm (“high” load), with an R-ratio of 0.1. These load levels were chosen to be just below, and substantially above, the quasi-static matrix crack threshold of about 27 Nm for this laminate. Strain was measured by a surface mounted extensometer, acting on the compression side of the samples in the central region, as shown in Figure 1. The extensometer output, which indicates the strain along a chord of a circle, was converted appropriately, taking into account the large deflections in the four-point bend test, to calculate the true flexural modulus of the coupon.

Figure 1. Schematic (not to scale) of the four-point bending experimental set up.

In the quasi-static tests, cross head displacements of 0.1 mms^{-1} were used. In order to measure the residual flexural modulus of the damaged material at regular stages of the damage evolution, discrete load increments were applied sequentially to the specimens. At each step, an increase in the crack density, which developed in the double thickness 90° ply under tension, was recorded using a digital video camera. In addition, a separate quasi-static test was carried out after each load step in order to measure the current residual flexural modulus of the specimens. Similar flexural modulus measurements were made during the fatigue tests after an appreciable increase in the crack density within the 90° ply as a consequence of fatigue loading.

Differential interference contrast microscopy was undertaken on suitable edge sections from both quasi-static and fatigue specimens in order to monitor the changes in crack morphology. In particular, polished edges of the damaged transverse ply were examined so that the development of matrix cracking across the transverse ply thickness could be observed.

3. RESULTS

3.1 Damage development

Matrix crack accumulation occurred with increasing bending moment in the 90° ply that was on the tensile side of the coupon. For quasi-static loading, the relationship between the increase in crack density and the applied bending moment is shown Figure 2. Cracks initiated at an applied bending moment of about 27 Nm and crack accumulation occurred rapidly with increasing bending moment to a crack density of about 0.4 mm^{-1} , which represents a crack spacing of just over two transverse ply thicknesses. Fatigue cycling was carried out with a peak loading of either 26.5 Nm (the “low” load case, just below the quasi-static cracking threshold) or 34 Nm (the “high” load case which corresponds to a crack density of about 0.3 mm^{-1} in quasi-static loading). The increase in crack

density in fatigue for these two load levels is illustrated in Figure 3. It can be seen that 10,000 cycles at the “high” load level produces a crack density of about 0.5 mm^{-1} , which corresponds to a crack spacing of about two transverse ply thicknesses.

Figure 2. Increase in crack density as a function of increasing bending moment for quasi-static loading

Figure 3. Increase in crack density with number of cycles for “low” and “high” load levels in fatigue loading

Under quasi-static loading, all the cracks initiated from the edges of the coupon. An example of the crack development (see Figure 4) shows a plan view of the specimen including the 50 mm gauge length extensometer. Crack development in quasi-static loading occurred in a stick-slip manner: once initiated, the cracks did not grow across the full specimen width instantaneously but, in general, grew part-way across the width, and an increased bending moment was required to propagate the cracks across the rest of the coupon. The arrows in Figure 4 show two cracks that initiated from opposite edges of the coupon. These cracks were sufficiently close that after meeting they “shielded” each other, with the consequence that crack growth was arrested. Any cracks spaced less than 1 mm apart (*i.e.* about 1 transverse ply thickness) were completely arrested in their growth across the coupon in this way. This is very similar to the behaviour of transverse ply cracks during tensile loading¹¹. For any larger spacing between cracks, the individual crack growth continued when the bending moment was increased, and the cracks grew to the opposite edge of the specimen.

Figure 4. Crack development during quasi-static loading. The sequence of images shows crack accumulation during an increasing applied bending moment. Arrows indicate cracks which eventually become “shielded.”
(a): 25.6 Nm; **(b):** 28.2 Nm; **(c)** 30.3 Nm; **(d):** 31.3 Nm.
 (Specimen width = 20 mm)

Sectioning of coupons and optical microscopy was carried out in order to examine the crack geometry at various stages of development. The microscopy revealed that crack growth across the thickness of the transverse ply starts from the interface between the transverse ply and the outer longitudinal ply on the tensile face of the coupon. The cracks grow both across the specimen width and across the transverse ply thickness, and after the crack has grown about 1 mm across the specimen width, the crack growth across the full thickness of the transverse ply is complete (the full transverse ply thickness is also 1 mm). Figure 5 shows an edge section with two cracks visible, one of which has partially grown across the 90° ply thickness. Similar crack development occurs for cracks initiated away from the coupon edges (initiation of cracks away from the coupon edges was only observed in fatigue loading). For cracks developing away from the coupon edges, crack initiation again occurs at the interface between the outer 0° ply and the adjacent 90° ply, and cracks develop with an approximately thumb-nail shape, growing both across the thickness of the 90° ply and across the coupon width.

Figure 5. Optical micrograph of an edge section of the cross-ply laminate showing a crack that has grown fully across the ply thickness (A) and a crack that has grown part-way across (B)

Figure 6. Delamination development at coupon edge and surface fibre bundle fracture after fatigue cycles at 34 Nm (“high” load).
(a): 4,000 cycles.**(b):** 10,000 cycles.

In fatigue loading, delaminations developed at the edge of the coupons where the matrix cracks met the 0/90 interface between the 90⁰ ply and the outer 0⁰ ply. An example of these delaminations is shown in Figure 6 for a coupon fatigued at the “high” load level after 4000 and 10,000 cycles. In addition to the delaminations, fracture of surface 0⁰ fibre bundles also developed near the coupon edge on the tensile face. This is believed to be fatigue failure of the 0⁰ tows.

A distinctive feature of the matrix crack development during fatigue loading, which makes it different from the quasi-static crack development, is the initiation of matrix cracking away from the coupon edges. Crack development of this type is shown in Figure 7. Crack arrest due to shielding of closely spaced cracks was again evident, and an example is shown in Figure 7(d).

Figure 7. Crack initiation in fatigue loading. The arrows show cracks that have initiated away from the coupon edges. The two cracks to the right of the pictures are sufficiently closely spaced to “shield” each other.
(a): 5000 cycles; **(b):** 6000 cycles; **(c):** 7000 cycles; **(d):** 10,000 cycles.

3.2 Changes in residual flexural modulus with crack accumulation

For both the quasi-static static and fatigue tests, the flexural modulus was determined as a function of matrix crack density. The reduction in normalised flexural modulus of the coupons (ie the current

flexural modulus divided by the initial undamaged flexural modulus) has been plotted against the crack density and the results are shown in Figure 8. In the same figure, the predictions of a model described in [8] are shown for comparison.

It can be seen that the predictions of the reduction in flexural modulus with increasing crack density are in reasonably good agreement for the coupons subjected to quasi-static loading. For the fatigue loading at the “low” load level, the agreement between the predictions and the data is again reasonably good, although there is somewhat more scatter in the data. The agreement is poorer in the results for the “high” fatigue loading case. The experimental flexural modulus in this case is generally about 2% lower than the prediction. However, it was at the “high” fatigue load level that extensive delamination developed from the coupon edges and observations of what appeared to be fatigue failure of surface bundles of 0^0 fibres were made. Clearly, these additional forms of damage will contribute to an additional reduction in the flexural modulus that has not been included in the model presented in [8].

Figure 8. Experimental data, and theoretical prediction from [8], for the flexural modulus reduction as a function of crack density for the (0/90₂/0/90₂/0) GFRP laminate.

5. CONCLUSIONS

The matrix cracking development in one transverse ply of a multiple cross-ply glass/epoxy laminate has been examined under flexural loading. Matrix crack development in these specimens, which have thick transverse plies, invariably occurs for quasi-static loading from the specimen edges and cracks grow in a stick-slip manner across the coupons. In fatigue loading, cracks also initiated away from the coupon edges and grew stably across the coupon. In all cases, cracks initiated near the 0/90 interface on the tensile side of the coupon and grew as rapidly across the transverse ply thickness as across the coupon width. For specimens fatigued at a “high” load level, delaminations developed

from matrix cracks at the coupon edge. In addition, some evidence of the fatigue failure of surface 0° fibre bundles at the coupon edges was seen.

Reductions in flexural modulus as a function of matrix crack density were in good agreement with previously published predictions, except for the “high” fatigue load level where additional damage leads to larger modulus reductions.

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